

Stimulating effect of giant African snail substrate and native mucus on the rhizogenesis of hybrid *Bacopa* cuttings during autumn-winter

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Abstract. The work was carried out within the framework of the social project “Touching Flowerbed”, where the school grows plants for six state educational institutions to assist with annual landscaping. In autumn 2024, hybrid *Bacopa* was chosen as the experimental plant. The project faced several challenges: the high cost of *Bacopa* seedlings in Sevastopol; the need for affordable, natural, and effective biostimulants for the propagation of valuable ornamental crops during autumn-winter; and the issue of organic waste disposal from giant African snails (*Achatina fulica*) kept at home (coconut substrate with waste products).

The present work includes the results of a two-season double experiment on autumn-winter rooting of *Bacopa* cuttings.

Aim – to evaluate the effect of snail-conditioned substrate and native snail mucus on the rooting and development of hybrid *Bacopa* cuttings under autumn-winter conditions.

Tasks:

1. Study the biology of *Achatina fulica* and *Bacopa hybrida*.
2. Conduct two consecutive rooting experiments.
3. Analyse and compare the results of the two experimental cycles.
4. Formulate recommendations for using snail waste products in plant propagation.

Object of study – hybrid *Bacopa* (*Bacopa hybrida*).

Subject of study – rhizogenesis of hybrid *Bacopa* cuttings.

Methods: observation, experiment (first and second), comparative analysis, statistical data processing (rooting percentage).

Hypothesis: The substrate from snail enclosures and native snail mucus positively affect the rhizogenesis of hybrid *Bacopa* during autumn-winter cuttings.

Results: Experiment No. 1 (2024–2025): rooting in water – 0%, in peat – 40%, in snail-conditioned substrate – 60%.

Experiment No. 2 (2025–2026): rooting with aloe vera juice – 40%, with *Achatina* mucus – 83%, with common street snail mucus – 60%.

Conclusion: The hypothesis is confirmed. Both the substrate and native mucus of giant African snails stimulate autumn-winter rooting of hybrid *Bacopa*. A method of direct mucus application was proposed and tested. An effective, eco-friendly technique for off-season *Bacopa* propagation was developed, turning snail waste into a valuable resource. The mechanism of action requires further investigation.

Keywords: *Achatina fulica*, *Bacopa hybrida*, snail mucus, rhizogenesis, circular economy

Introduction

The “Touching Flowerbed” project has been active at School No. 57 since 2019. Students grow plants for six kindergartens in the city, including inclusive groups for children with visual impairments. During autumn and winter, propagation of ornamental crops, especially hybrid *Bacopa* (*Bacopa hybrida*), becomes difficult: cuttings root poorly, and purchased seedlings are expensive. At the same time, many students keep giant African snails (*Achatina fulica*) at home, generating organic waste (used coconut substrate and mucus secreted by snails for regeneration). We hypothesised that these waste products could serve as natural rooting stimulants.

Aim – to evaluate the effect of snail-conditioned substrate and native snail mucus on the rooting of hybrid *Bacopa* cuttings during autumn-winter.

Tasks:

1. Review the biology of *Achatina fulica* and *Bacopa hybrida*.
2. Perform two sequential rooting experiments.
3. Compare results and develop recommendations.

Materials and Methods

Experiment No. 1 (2024–2025)

Bacopa cuttings (5–7 cm long, 10 per group) were rooted in three media:

- water (control),
- standard peat (commonly used in the project),
- used coconut substrate from snail enclosures (containing snail waste).

Cuttings were placed in containers; humidity was maintained, temperature kept at +16...+18°C.

Rooting was recorded after 61 days.

Experiment No. 2 (2025–2026)

Cuttings (12 per group) were planted in identical coconut substrate but treated with different substances before planting:

- aloe vera juice (traditional folk remedy),
- native *Achatina mucus* (collected directly from snails),
- mucus from common street snails (collected outdoors).

Conditions were the same as in the first experiment. Rooting was evaluated after 61 days.

Results

Experiment No. 1

- Water: no roots (0%).
- Peat: 40% rooting.
- Snail-conditioned substrate: 60% rooting .

This showed that the used substrate outperforms ordinary peat.

Experiment No. 2

- Aloe vera juice: 40% rooting.
- Street snail mucus: 60% rooting.
- *Achatina mucus*: 83% rooting .

Thus, the mucus of giant African snails proved the most effective. All roots were well developed, with no signs of rot.

Discussion

The results support the hypothesis that giant African snail waste products stimulate rooting. The used substrate, enriched with organic matter, creates a favourable environment for root formation. Snail mucus contains bioactive compounds such as allantoin, collagen, and antimicrobial peptides, which promote cell division, protect against pathogens, and enhance tissue regeneration. The higher efficiency of *Achatina mucus* compared to street snail mucus may be due to species-specific biochemical adaptations for shell regeneration.

Practical significance:

- A free, accessible, and eco-friendly rooting stimulant has been identified.
- The method utilises snail waste that would otherwise be discarded.
- The technique is already used in the “Touching Flowerbed” project for off-season propagation of ornamental plants.

Further research should focus on the exact mechanism of action and the potential application of this method for other difficult-to-root species, including Red List plants (e.g., *Vitex agnus-castus*).

Conclusion

The two-season experiment demonstrated that used coconut substrate and native mucus of giant African snails positively influence the rhizogenesis of hybrid *Bacopa* during autumn-winter. The substrate increased rooting to 60% (vs. 40% in peat), and snail mucus achieved 83% rooting (vs. 40% with aloe vera). The proposed method requires no chemical stimulants and turns waste into a valuable resource, aligning with circular economy principles.

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